

D4.9 Open Data Access Point **Workpackage 4**

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners:

University of Surrey, Sciensano

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D4.9 Open Data Access Point
WP and Task	WP4; Task 4.5.3
Leader	SVA
Other contributors	University of Surrey (Jade Passey, Piyali Basu) and Sciensano (Valerie de Waele)
Due month of the deliverable	M12
Actual submission month	M13 (website), M14 (report)
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	OTHER and R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

OPEN DATA ACCESS POINT

Background

A core feature of the dissemination strategy of the One Health EJP (OHEJP) is to make its outputs openly accessible, as far as possible; i.e. they should be easy to find, copy, distribute, search, link, crawl and mine. This ambition pertains to all types of outputs; deliverables in all their respective forms as well as publications with underlying data, and other data generated through the research. All of the above are an important means to maximise impact.

The open data strategy is also in line with Horizon 2020 expectations, where projects from 1st January 2017 are participating in the Open Research Data Pilot within [OpenAIRE](#). The implementation is guided, in parts, by the [OHEJP Data Management Plan](#) (DMP). Adherence to the DMP is governed by the Consortium Agreement. The DMP covers strategies related to management and access of data; both so-called 'underlying data' (on which scientific publications are based), and other types of data (metadata, raw data). The overarching purpose is to preserve data generated by Joint Research and Integrative Projects as well as PhD projects in a format that will allow future consultation and use.

The implementation of the open data strategy is also governed by the open access publication policy, which ensures that all scientific peer-reviewed publications produced within the OHEJP can be read online, downloaded and printed at the time of publication (green or gold open access).

WP4 of the OHEJP is responsible for the DMP and for the publication policy, and also has the task of making it easy to direct interested parties to the joint output of the OHEJP. This is expressed in subtask 4.5.3 Open data access point (ODAP), which promises to deliver an access point for open data on the website of the EJP, to be developed in collaboration with the WP1 Communications Team. The purpose of the ODAP is to function as a one-stop shop for the openly available digital output of the OHEJP. In other words, by visiting the ODAP, it should be possible to reach everything that the OHEJP has produced in an easy and understandable way.

The implementation of the first version of the ODAP was finalised in M13. It will be updated and developed further according to the needs of the OHEJP. This document describes its current (M14) location, functionality and layout.

The ODAP can be seen as consisting of three parts:

1. The user interface on the webpage,
2. The OpenAIRE | EXPLORE Dashboard, where the output related to the OHEJP is indexed and summarised, provided it has been uploaded on...
3. ...Zenodo, the platform where the output is made available.

1. The user interface

At current, the website visitor reaches the ODAP via the 'Projects' landing page. An announcement at the top of the page signals that this is a new functionality (since M13) (Fig. 1). (This feature will subsequently be removed.) The ODAP web interface is found further down on the same webpage (see Fig 2 below).

Figure 1. 'Projects' landing page and announcement of the ODAP feature.

Figure 2. ODAP button inviting the website visitor to access the OHEJP OpenAIRE dashboard.

By clicking on the ODAP button, the visitor is linked to the OHEJP's OpenAIRE | EXPLORE Dashboard.

2. The OpenAIRE | EXPLORE Dashboard

The EXPLORE Dashboard (Fig. 3) is a part of the OpenAIRE resources that allows the visitor to get an overview of a project and its output. It is also possible to communicate from OpenAIRE, share output via social media and similar. Basically, OpenAIRE provides functionality to search, share and link the project output but is not the place where they are physically stored, and available for download. The OpenAIRE dashboard also provides links to the partners in the OHEJP – not to their own webpages, but to information about previous and current projects that the partner has been involved in, and that has been financed by funders that are part of OpenAIRE (and in particular EU funded projects).

Figure 3. The upper part of the One Health EJP OpenAIRE Dashboard.

3. Zenodo, a multi-modal repository

The functionality to store research output, and make it accessible, is provided by Zenodo, a platform supporting open science, built and developed by CERN (the institute for particle physics) as part of the OpenAIRE project (Fig. 4). CERN has been a pioneer in open source, open access and open data. Zenodo was launched in May 2013, and makes it possible for scholars to share, curate and publish all types of research output, including data and software. In other words, Zenodo is free of charge and does not impose any requirements on format, size, access restrictions or licence.

Zenodo also helps in making the project outputs citable, and through OpenAIRE integrates them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission. This means that publications uploaded in this manner, and identified as an output of the OHEJP, will automatically appear on the H2020 portal, and thereby facilitate the reporting. Citation information is also passed to DataCite (the leading global non-profit organisation that provides persistent identifiers (DOIs) for research data) and onto the scholarly aggregators.

In fact, Zenodo also offers the possibility to house closed and restricted content, so that artefacts can be captured and stored safely whilst the research is ongoing, such that nothing is missing when they are openly shared later in the research workflow. Research materials for the review process can also be safely uploaded to Zenodo in restricted records and then protected links can be shared with the reviewers. Content can also be embargoed and automatically opened when the associated paper is published.

The screenshot shows a Zenodo record page for a document titled "Data Management Plan for One Health European Joint Program". The page is dated June 30, 2018, and is marked as a "Project deliverable" and "Open Access". It has 9 views and 6 downloads. The author is listed as Valérie De Waele. The document is indexed in OpenAIRE. The DOI is 10.5281/zenodo.2541570. The keywords are "data management plan", "One Health EJP", "OHEJP", "overarching DMP", and "DMP". The grants listed are from the European Commission, specifically for "One Health EJP - Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards. (773830)". The license is Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. A preview of the document is shown, featuring the ne HEALTHEJP logo.

Figure 4. Output from the OHEJP made accessible via Zenodo, a catch-all repository for open science.

The use of Zenodo is described in D4.7 'Guidelines for Data Management Plan implementation of One Health EJP projects' which is available on.... Zenodo! <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572989>

There maybe reasons for choosing other repositories than Zenodo for making research outputs available, for example data archives or repositories already established for a particular research domain to preserve the data according to recognized standards, like the European Nuclotide Archive- ENA, or GenBank. Alternatively, there may be institutional research data repositories or national repositories that should be used based on requirements from the national confunder. This detail of information can be found in the project-specific DMP:s. From an open data access point-of-view, these data sources should still be made findable in relation to the OHEJP using the linking functionality of the OpenAIRE dashboard.

If other repositories than OHEJP Zenodo are used, they should meet the following criteria:

- Provide a persistent and unique identifier.
- Provide a landing page for each dataset, with metadata that helps others find it, tell what it is, relate it to publications, and cite it.
- Help to track how the data has been used by providing access and download statistics.
- Be considered a trustworthy data repository, with an explicit ambition to keep the data available in the long term.
- Match particular data needs (e.g. formats accepted, access, backup, recovery and sustainability of the service).
- Offer clear terms and conditions that meet legal requirements (e.g. for data protection) and allow reuse without unnecessary licensing conditions.
- Provide guidance on how to cite the data that has been deposited.

4. Next steps

OHEJP partners and researchers are still learning to work in this new digital scholarly environment, and developing and implementing project-specific data management plans is an important step in this direction. OHEJP WP4 continues to support this process.

The OHEJP Management is currently also clarifying and streamlining the processes for making the deliverables and publications findable and accessible, and subsequently it will also be ensured that data underlying OHEJP publication are openly available, interoperable and reusable, if the conditions so allow. The decision to make research data openly available is guided by the arguments described in the project-specific data management plans.

Furthermore, the location of the ODAP is likely to change as the website is developed to specifically list and link to project outputs under a dedicated page (Resources or Output).

Therefore, the process of making OHEJP outputs openly available is ongoing, and there will be an iterative process to develop this functionality further.